

DEVELOPMENT OF MANAGEMENT OF ECONOMIC COMPETENCE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE REGIONS

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In the conditions of current economic development, in the modern stage of world development, the development of the industrial sectors of the countries is taking place in the conditions of effective use of available resources on the one hand, and ensuring the competitiveness of production in the context of innovative technologies and high level of specialization on the other hand. As a whole, the share of industry in the total volume of world GDP is the highest in the countries of the Middle East, East Asia and South Africa, and according to the World Bank, industrial production and employment have a high impact on the economy of each country.

In addition, the Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026 states that in order to strengthen the responsibility and accountability of the state administration bodies in solving territorial issues based on the principle of "State - for people" and to create a new system aimed at planning their strategic directions, one of the state administration bodies at all levels development of the annual work program, including with the participation of the public, establishing the practice of constantly announcing the status of their implementation, public monitoring of the process of implementation of the decisions taken by the state administration bodies, including the creation of a system of regular announcements in mass media [1].

In modernizing Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to quality indicators such as modernization of economic sectors, qualitative development based on modern requirements, wide introduction of innovative technologies in production, ensuring competitiveness of production in the world market based on digital and innovative technologies.

In order to solve these tasks, researching the scientific-methodical and practical aspects of managing the economic potential of production in industrial enterprises is

urgent. It is of great importance to express the full content of the "economic efficiency" category in order to clarify the essence of increasing economic efficiency in the production process.

A.N. Khramtsova and A.A. In the research carried out by Akhmatova, it is possible to divide the definitions given by economists into the following three groups in the process of explaining the content of the economic category of innovation in the process of enterprise management:

- explaining the content of the economic category of innovation in connection with innovation, know-how;
- explaining the content of innovation as a whole process that incorporates the production of a new product, including its technical and technological features;
- evaluation of the content of innovation, related to the implementation of new ideas and thoughts, as well as the driving force for the production of improved products in a new form [2, 18].

Innovative potential - development of new developments, discoveries or inventions, creation of useful models of an enterprise or organization or, in general, any business entity, regardless of the branch, field of activity, ownership form, organizational-legal status, size, is the sum of all available intellectual, financial, personnel, information, material and technical and other resources and opportunities for their effective use in their current activities [3,8].

Based on the conducted research, it should be noted that innovative activity is an independent category, characterized by the effectiveness and regularity of innovations, the dynamics of actions to create and implement innovations. (Table 1).

Table 1

Managing the principles of increasing economic potential in industrial enterprises*

Collective principle	Management of a wide and comprehensive analysis of indicators that determine the main aspects of the economic potential of the enterprise
The principle of expediency	Manage relevance and effectiveness for future plans and objectives based on indicators that influence economic growth

The principle of objectivity	Calculation of economic efficiency improvement and evaluation methods based on analysis with accurate and reliable data
The principle of systematicity	Management of the system of interrelated and complementary indicators of economic potential
Efficiency Principle	Ensuring positive, beneficial results and efficiency expected to be achieved by increasing economic efficiency in an enterprise or organization
Optimality Principle	Achieving the goal based on the use of accurate, correct and optimal indicators of economic potential
Priority Principle	Formation of an innovative tendency as a result of modernizing the production process, increasing the product quality and stimulating the skills of the employees in the future by increasing the economic efficiency of the enterprise.

*** Author development based on data**

It is possible to assess the level of innovative activity in industrial enterprises, its competitiveness and, as a result, the overall level of development. The higher the innovative activity of the enterprise, the more intensive its innovative activity. The group of main principles of increasing and improving the economic efficiency of the enterprise was systematized as follows.

In 2007, due to the analysis of changes in the production of industrial products, modernization and diversification of industrial potential and industrial enterprises, the production of high-added-value industrial and consumer products, and the launch of high-tech modern enterprises, the volume of gross domestic product production in 2007 was 163147.0 mln. amounted to 21,314.2 billion soums, and in 2022, the gross regional domestic product produced by the region was 21,314.2 billion. amounted to soums (Table 2).

Table 2

**Industrial products in the sector of enterprises in Jizzakh region
production volume (billion soums)**

Indicators	2018 й.	2020 й.	2022 й.
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	Product volume, billion soum	growth, %	Product volume, billion soum	growth, %	Product volume, billion soum	growth, %
Total industry products production volume	2 548,8	172,8	3 581,8	140,5	4 586,5	128,0
Large enterprises: including:	919,3	118,4	118,4 1	129,5	1 948,7	163,6
Textiles	229,8	29,6	297,75	32,7	487,127	40,9
Metallurgy	383,1	49,39	496,25	53,7	811,85	68,17
Food	306,4	39,46	397,0	43,1	649,79	54,53
Small business	1 629,5	233,4	390,8	146,7	638,015	110,3

* Prepared by the author based on the data of the General Directorate of Statistics of Jizzakh region.

Table 2 shows that the total production volume of industrial products in Jizzakh region in 2018 was 2,548.8 billion. amounted to 4,586.5 billion soums in 2022. to soums, and compared to 2020, it increased by 128.0%.

The experience of the developed countries of the world shows that the formation and development of industry in the economy of a certain region requires that the level of development of the industrial sectors of the national economy is compatible. It is legitimate to strategically determine the development of the state based on its material and intellectual potential, and then to use the efficient, intensive factors of industry.

In the development of industry, the establishment of new industries, the development of existing industries, the structural restructuring of the economy, as well as the establishment of production infrastructure, the creation of an intellectual base that manages industrial enterprises and provides new production. The theoretical

importance of the classification of factors affecting the efficiency of industrial enterprises is that it allows to fully reveal the essence of efficiency, to determine the ratio between factors, and to clarify the characteristics of the influence of individual factors, taking into account certain directions of the enterprise's activity. Accordingly, the classification of physiological, technical-technological, organizational, economic, social-psychological factors affecting economic efficiency in industrial enterprises based on their economic essence was developed.

Based on the conducted researches, through the organization of associations of industrial enterprises engaged in innovative activities, in addition to increasing the speed of mutual transfer of innovations, it will be possible to further develop innovative cooperation relations between enterprises. In order to increase the economic potential of industrial enterprises, it is necessary to implement the following measures:

- increase the level of implementation of innovative projects by industrial enterprises;
- expansion of international cooperation on the implementation of innovative projects among industrial enterprises;
- acceleration of mutual transfer of innovations between industrial enterprises;
- conducting innovative marketing research in the regions;
- formation of requirements for new innovative projects;
- increase the efficiency of using internal and external opportunities in the development of innovative activities of industrial enterprises

In our opinion, by implementing the organizational and economic mechanism of increasing the efficiency of innovative management of industrial enterprises proposed above, in the long-term perspective, the level of innovative activity of industrial enterprises of our country will increase and the possibilities of implementing innovations will expand.

Also, the indicators of the efficiency of the programs for supporting the innovative activities of industrial enterprises will increase, and the indicators of the competitiveness of the produced products in the international markets will improve.

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